

RESULT 1 - CERTIFICATION CENTRE

To access the documentation related to the justification of the results obtained in relation to *ACTIVITY 1: Creation and implementation of 3 Regional Centres for Youth Training in Digital and Sustainable Entrepreneurship (DSE) for NEETs in Greece, Spain and Romania*, please click on the following links:

[Result 1 - Certification Centre](#)

[Task 1 - Operational Procedures](#)

[Task 2 - Non-formal microcredentials Procedures](#)

[Task 3 - Center Launch](#)

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